

Flavonoids from *Eruca sativa* Mill

W. Rahman, M. Ilyas and J. N. Usmani

On account of immense therapeutic value *Eruca sativa* was subjected to extensive chemical investigation. Although the seeds and leaves of the genus were examined for the isolation of various plant products, no work seems to have been done for the detection of flavonoids.

The ethanol extract of the defatted and dried leaves was subjected to solvent fractionation followed by chromatography on magnesium silicate, yielded a free aglycone m.p. 304–306° (ethanol) and a glycoside 165–67° (ethanol). The homogeneity of the products was established by paper chromatography in two different solvent systems and also by T.L.C.

The free aglycone m.p. 304–306°¹ has been characterized as 3'-methoxy-4',5,7-trihydroxy flavonol (iso-rhamnetin) by its melting and mixed melting points, formation of its acetate m.p. 203–204°² (alcohol), R_f -values and co-chromatography. The identity of the aglycone as isorahmnetin has been further evidenced by spectral studies, the light absorption in the ultraviolet region λ_{max}^{EtOH} 265 μ , 375 μ and I.R. absorption : ν_{max}^{Nujol} 1655 and 3160 cm^{-1} .

The glycoside gave positive cyanidin test³ both in acid as well as in alkaline media. Wilson boric acid test⁴ confirmed it to be a flavonol-3-glycoside. On hydrolysis it gave an aglycone m.p. 304–306° and a sugar. The aglycone has been identified as isorahmnetin as described earlier and the sugar as glucose by R_f value and co-chromatography on Whatman Paper No. 1 as well as by T.L.C. The glycoside gave an acetate m.p. 135–36° (ethanol), which on deacetylation furnished the original glycoside m.p. 165–67°.

The methylation of glycoside followed by hydrolysis gave 3',4',5,7-tetramethyl quercetin¹ m.p. 192–94° (EtOH) locating sugar moiety at C₃. The quantitative estimation of sugar by Somogyi's copper micro method⁵ showed the presence of one mole of sugar per mole of aglycone. The glycoside m.p. 165–67° is therefore characterized as isorhamnetin-3-glucoside.

1. G. E. Inglet, *Nature*, 1956, **178**, 1346.
2. M. B. Moore and E. E. Moore, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, **53**, 2744.
3. Y. Asahina and M. Inubuse, *Chem. Ber.*, 1928, **61B**, 1646.
4. C. W. Wilson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **61**, 2303.
5. M. Somogyi, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1952, **195**, 19.